

Direct Calculation of the Zero Power Neutron Noise Rossi- α , Feynman Variance-to-Mean and Double Counting Rate

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ABSTRACT

Neutron density in zero power nuclear systems fluctuates due to random nuclear processes, but these fluctuations contain valuable information. Both induced and spontaneous fission produce time-correlated neutron emissions, which can reveal properties of fissile materials. Since the 1950s, several time-correlation (or “neutron noise”) techniques have been developed to extract this information from detector signals using specialized algorithms. However, traditional Monte Carlo simulations for these methods are computationally expensive. This paper introduces a “direct method” that exploits the Monte Carlo simulation’s inherent ability to trace each neutron’s origin, allowing correlated detections from the same fission chain to be identified directly. This approach enables faster calculation of time-correlated quantities.

Keywords: Direct method, Neutron noise

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron density in zero-power nuclear systems fluctuates due to the inherently random nature of nuclear processes. However, within this apparent noise lies valuable information. Both induced and spontaneous fissions emit bursts of prompt neutrons within very short time intervals, producing groups of temporally correlated neutrons. These processes also generate delayed neutrons, which introduce additional time correlations over much longer timescales. To extract this correlated information—providing insight into the fissile material content—various time-correlation techniques have been developed since the 1950s [1, 2, 3], such as the Rossi- α , the Feynman Variance-to-Mean, and the Neutron Multiplicity Counting (NMC) methods.

Typically, time-correlation quantities obtained from simulations are evaluated using algorithms analogous to those applied to experimental detector data, relying solely on detection times. This approach, referred to here as the analog method, requires a detailed, event-by-event simulation of neutron transport (i.e., a fixed-source analog calculation). Consequently, conventional Monte Carlo variance-reduction techniques (e.g., Russian roulette, splitting, etc.), which preserve only first-order moments, cannot be applied.

As a result, despite modern increases in computational power, neutron noise simulations can still be highly CPU-intensive, especially for configurations involving numerous neutron interactions, extended time ranges, or low detection efficiencies.

This paper introduces an alternative approach that leverages additional information inherently available in source-fixed analog simulations—specifically, neutron genealogies. Most Monte Carlo transport codes provide a history or fission-chain identifier, which can be used to directly identify correlated detections (i.e., those originating from the same fission chain). This approach is hereafter referred to as

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the *direct method*. This paper focuses on the calculation of the single counting rate, the double counting rate, the Rossi- α curve and the Feynman Variance-to-Mean method [4] [5].

The first part of the present paper recalls the methodology of the *analog method*, then the theory of the *direct method* is described and is applied to a real experiment in the last part.

2. ANALOG METHOD (REMINDER)

This section recalls the basic principles needed to introduce the *direct method* formalism in the following section. During a analog fixed source simulation, neutron detections are time-stamped and stored in a file, forming the so-called *signal*, which thus consists of a series of detection times. In a subsequent step, post-processing algorithms—often identical to those used for experimental detector data—are applied to the signal. These algorithms sample the detection times to construct the desired statistical distributions.

One approach is to build the time distribution of the duration between two different detections resulting in the so-called Rossi- α curve. This curve (Q) is the sum of an uncorrelated component (Q_a or “accidental correlations” which are detections that do not belong to the same fission chain - a constant term) and a correlated term (Q_r or “real correlations”).

Another approach is to sample the signal into equal samples of width τ (so called time gates). For each of them the number of events are counted and binned into a histogram called the Feynman histogram. This histogram therefore represents the occurrence probabilities of various multiplets (i.e., 1 detection, 2 detections, etc.) occurring within a specified time gate width τ . From these histograms the $c_k(\tau)$ values representing the number of times k detections are found in time gates of width τ are deduced. This can be repeated for multiple time gates widths resulting in multiple Feynman histograms. The NMC values are finally calculated with the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} m_1(\tau) &= \frac{\sum_k k c_k(\tau)}{\sum_k c_k(\tau)} & m_2(\tau) &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sum_k k(k-1)c_k(\tau)}{\sum_k c_k(\tau)} \\ Y_1(\tau) &= \frac{m_1(\tau)}{\tau} & Y_2(\tau) &= \frac{1}{\tau} \left(m_2(\tau) - \frac{1}{2} m_1(\tau) \right) \\ Y(\tau) &= 2 \frac{Y_2(\tau)}{Y_1(\tau)} & Y(\tau) &= \frac{\text{var}(c_k(\tau))}{\text{mean}(c_k(\tau))} - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Where Y_1 and Y_2 stand for the single and double counting rates for time gates of width τ , m_1 and m_2 being the first two reduced factorial moments as expressed, for example, in the Hage-Cifarelli formalism. Y is the Feynman Variance-to-Mean.

Since $Y_1(\tau)$ is simply the count rate, its value should remain constant regardless of the time gates width values (as long as it is sufficiently large to avoid statistical effect) and is equal to a named value R_1 . Changing τ allows to adjust the amount of detections coming from the same fission chains (i.e. correlated detections) taken into account. If τ tends towards zero the probability of having correlated detections also tends towards zero as well as $Y_2(\tau)$ and $Y(\tau)$. As τ increases, more and more correlated detections are included in a time gate leading to an increase of $Y_2(\tau)$ and $Y(\tau)$. At first, only correlated detections from prompt neutrons contribute to $Y_2(\tau)$ and $Y(\tau)$. For higher τ values, all neutrons (prompt + delayed) will contribute. This is shown by the presence of two plateaus on the Feynman curve (Fig. 1). Further increase of τ does not add more correlated detection and both $Y_2(\tau)$ and $Y(\tau)$ tend to their asymptotic values respectively named R_2 and Y_∞ .

3. THE PROPOSED DIRECT METHOD

Let S be the mean rate of source events (i.e. the mean number of histories per time unit) and p_N the probability for a history to create N detections. The first value is an input data required to make the

Figure 1. Feynman Variance-to-Mean curve as a function of the time gate width τ

simulation and the second one may easily be estimated from the simulation results. In particular, the association of each detection with the fission chain identifier makes it possible to calculate the p_N quantity. That being said, for a stationary process the mean rate of detections from histories creating N detections is $S \cdot p_N \cdot C_N^1$ where C denotes the binomial coefficient. Summing over all possible numbers of detections gives the single rate of detections:

$$\mathring{Y}_1 = S \sum_{N=1}^{\infty} p_N C_N^1 \quad (1)$$

In this formula as well as in the following ones, the circle denotes values calculated using the *direct method*. It should be noted that \mathring{Y}_1 does not depend on the time-gate width, unlike Y_1 , for which the gate width has a statistical effect. Therefore, by analogy to the *analog method*, $\mathring{R}_1 = \mathring{Y}_1$. The expected number of detections per time gates \mathring{m}_1 is obtained as $\mathring{Y}_1 \cdot \tau$, as it appears in the formulas presented in section 2. The same approach is then applied for the double counting rate. Considering the mean rate of correlated pairs triggered by the i th detection of histories creating N detections is $S \cdot p_N \cdot C_{N-i}^1$, the mean double counting rate created by histories having N detections is given by Eq. 2. Taking into account all histories with any number of detections gives the asymptotic mean double counting rate \mathring{R}_2 Eq. 3.

$$S p_N \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} C_{N-i}^1 = S p_N C_N^2 \quad (2) \quad \mathring{R}_2 = S \sum_{N=2}^{\infty} p_N C_N^2 \quad (3)$$

Contrary to the *analog method*, the *direct method* gives a direct access to the asymptotic double counting rate. We are now interested in the calculation of the non-asymptotic value of \mathring{R}_2 , i.e. $\mathring{Y}_2(\tau)$. Let's consider a first detection in the time range $[t_1, t_1 + dt_1]$ and a second one inside $[t_2, t_2 + dt_2]$ with $t_1 < t_2$. The average number of correlated pairs of detections \mathring{Q}_r between two correlated detections distant of $t_2 - t_1$ is:

$$\mathring{Q}_r(t_2 - t_1) dt_1 dt_2 = \mathring{R}_2 \text{pdf}(t_2 - t_1) dt_1 dt_2 \quad (4)$$

with pdf the probability density function of the time intervals between any pair of detections of an history i.e. the auto-correlation function. Once again the fission chain identifier provided by the simulation code allows for a direct estimate of the function pdf. Here we can note that \mathring{Q}_r is in fact the correlated component of the Rossi- α curve. With \mathring{Q}_r defined, one can now calculate \mathring{m}_{2r} which corresponds to the expected number of correlated pairs of detection in time gates of width τ . This is achieved by summing for each detection occurring at $t_1 \leq \tau$ the second detections occurring at $t_2 \leq \tau$:

$$\mathring{m}_{2r}(\tau) = \int_0^{\tau} dt_1 \int_{t_1}^{\tau} \mathring{Q}_r(t_2 - t_1) dt_2 = \mathring{R}_2 \int_0^{\tau} dt \int_0^{\tau-t} d\tau \text{pdf}(\tau) = \mathring{R}_2 \int_0^{\tau} \text{cdf}(t) dt$$

With cdf the cumulative density function of the time intervals between any pair of detections of an history. Combination of the previous equations gives the final expression of the doubles counting rate as calculated with the *direct method* :

$$\dot{Y}_2(\tau) = \frac{m_{2r}^{\circ}}{\tau} = \frac{R_2^{\circ}}{\tau} \int_0^{\tau} dt \text{cdf}(t)$$

Note that the definition of the Feynman Variance-to-Mean as two times the ratio between the double and single counting rate remains valid so that no specific derivation is required:

$$\dot{Y} = 2 \frac{R_2^{\circ}}{R_1^{\circ}} \qquad Y_{\infty}(\tau) = 2 \frac{\dot{Y}_2(\tau)}{\dot{Y}_1}$$

The above reasoning does not differentiate between types of neutron sources. For instance, if fission chains are created by both spontaneous fissions and (α , n) reactions, S combines these two types of sources. However, for practical reasons it is sometimes interesting to differentiate sources in simulations: one may perform a set of simulations with only spontaneous fission sources and another set of simulations with only (α , n) sources in order to later adjust the proportion of one source type to the other. Since each of these sources creates fission chains which are independent from each other, previous equations can be easily rewritten with source differentiation by considering that the total contribution is the sum of each individual contribution:

$$\begin{aligned} R_1^{\circ} = \dot{Y}_1 &= \sum_i (S_i \sum_{N=1}^{\infty} p_{i,N} \cdot C_N^1) & R_2^{\circ} &= \sum_i (S_i \sum_{N=2}^{\infty} p_{i,N} \cdot C_N^2) \\ \dot{Q}_r(t_2 - t_1) &= \sum_i (R_{2,i}^{\circ} \cdot \text{pdf}_i(t_2 - t_1) dt_1 dt_2) & \dot{Y}_2(\tau) &= \sum_i \left(\frac{R_{2,i}^{\circ}}{\tau} \int_0^{\tau} dt \cdot \text{cdf}_i(t) \right) \end{aligned}$$

with the subscript i denoting the contribution of the source of type i among I different sources. $\dot{Y}(\tau)$ is still calculated through two times the ratio of \dot{Y}_2 and \dot{Y}_1 and no specific derivation is required.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Case study

To illustrate the advantages of the *direct method* we consider the Sub-critical Copper-Reflected alpha-phase Plutonium (SCRA α P) integral benchmark experiment, designed and measured by the Los Alamos National Laboratory at the National Criticality Experiments Research Center (NCERC). It should be emphasized that this chapter does not aim to compare simulated and measured results (for such the reader may refer to [6]), but rather to compare simulated results obtained with and without the *direct method*. Details of the experiment are provided in [6] and illustrated in Fig. 2. The setup consists of a weapon-grade plutonium sphere surrounded by spherical shells of copper/polyethylene. Neutrons primarily originate from spontaneous fissions and (α , n) reactions. Correlated neutron measurements were performed using a detector system composed of ^3He tubes embedded in high-density polyethylene. Among the 16 different measured configurations, this work focuses on configuration No 15 which exhibits the highest keff value. This configuration consists of the plutonium sphere surrounded by a inner polyethylene layer approximately 1.18 cm thick (white region in Fig. 2) followed by an outer copper shell approximately 8.71 cm thick (gold color). Selecting the configuration with the highest reactivity facilitates the distinction between the delayed and prompt neutron components. The calculated keff using the Monte Carlo code MORET6 [7] is 0.944 ($\sigma = 100$ pcm).

(a) Configuration n°15 during assembly

(b) Experimental set up. The nuclear system is surrounded by the NOMAD detectors

 Figure 2. The SCRA α P experiment

4.2. General procedure for the calculation of the direct method

For the *direct method* the post-processing step requires only the detection times and the corresponding history identifiers for the calculation of p_N and $\text{pdf}(\tau)$. Since each recorded detection is associated with its corresponding history identifier, the calculation of p_N is straightforward. For the estimate of $\text{pdf}(\tau)$, all time intervals between every possible pair of detections originating from the same history are determined and subsequently combined across all histories. Special attention must be paid to the choice of binning when calculating $\text{pdf}(\tau)$, in order to properly capture both short and long time ranges corresponding to prompt and delayed neutrons, respectively. In the following comparison, the binning consists of 1000 logarithmically spaced values between 1.10^{-9} and 1.10^4 seconds.

4.3. Rossi- α comparison

According to the SCRA α P benchmark report [6], neutrons originate from approximately 128,500 spontaneous fissions per second and 4,200 (α, n) reactions per second. The duration of the simulated signal is about 5,500 seconds, corresponding to approximately $7 \cdot 10^8$ spontaneous fissions and $2.3 \cdot 10^7$ (α, n) reactions.

A first comparison is presented in Fig. 3a showing results for time-gate widths ranging from $1 \cdot 10^{-7}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ seconds. The *direct method* (\dot{Q}), shown in red is compared with the *analog method* (Q , shown in blue). Since the analog Rossi- α signal consists of both correlated and uncorrelated components (i.e. $Q = Q_r + Q_a$), while the direct Rossi- α includes only the correlated component (i.e. $\dot{Q} = \dot{Q}_r$), a virtual uncorrelated component is added to \dot{Q} to enable a consistent comparison. With \dot{Q}_a set to about $7.16 \cdot 10^9$, Fig. 3a shows an excellent agreement between both methods. Before further comparisons, it is useful to recall the operating principles of both calculation methods. The analog algorithm computes, for each detection, all time differences between this detection and the detections occurring within a given time gate. Consequently, it must account for both correlated and uncorrelated detections. In contrast, the direct algorithm, by exploiting the history identifiers, computes only the time differences between detections belonging to the same history—thus considering correlated detections only. This distinction implies that when the uncorrelated part of the Rossi- α curve dominates, the analog method spends a significant amount of computation time processing uncorrelated detections, which generally provide no useful information. As a result, for sufficiently large time-gate widths, the computational cost becomes too prohibitive. In the present case, the maximum feasible time-gate width does not allow the “delayed neutron” region of the curve to be computed. One way to overcome this limitation is to reduce the uncorrelated part, i.e. to decrease the overlap between fission chains. This can be achieved by reducing the neutron source intensity, thereby artificially extending the total signal duration while maintaining the same number of simulated histories. A new signal was therefore generated with a duration equal

to $5.5 \cdot 10^7$ seconds (about 640 days) corresponding to a fictive source composed of 12.85 spontaneous fissions per second and about 0.42 (α, n) reactions per second. Fig. 3b presents the result for time-gates widths ranging from $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $1 \cdot 10^2$ seconds. Using this approach, a perfect match between both methods is now observed across the entire curve, including the delayed neutron region — previously inaccessible in practice.

Figure 3. Rossi- α comparison between direct method and analog method (log-log scale)

4.4. $Y(\tau)$ and $\dot{Y}(\tau)$ mean values comparison

Taking into account a signal duration of 5 500 seconds with nominal intrinsic sources intensities, a first comparison is presented in Fig. 4a for time gates widths from $1 \cdot 10^{-7}$ to $1 \cdot 10^4$ seconds between the *direct method* (i.e. $\dot{Y}(\tau)$) in red and the *analog method* (i.e. $Y(\tau)$) in blue. For time gates width smaller than $1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ seconds both methods are in good agreement. Above this time gates width the *analog method* starts to exhibit large fluctuations (due to an insufficient number of time gates used to calculate the NMC values) while the *direct method* has a sufficient number of histories in the same calculation results, to keep a low uncertainty on the values.

For larger time gates widths, one possible way to make the comparison feasible - i.e. to obtain an exploitable curve with the *analog method* - is to extend the duration of the simulated signal by performing additional simulations. However, this approach is practically infeasible on standard desktop computers due to the extremely high computational cost, as it would require simulations several orders of magnitude longer. An alternative approach is to generate multiple independent signals by varying the random seed. The results of this method are presented in Fig. 4b, which shows the mean (blue curve) and the standard deviation of the $Y(\tau)$ values computed from a set of 100 independently generated signals. From this figure it can be inferred that the averaged *analog* $Y(\tau)$ values are consistent with those obtained using the *direct method* up to time-gate widths of approximately 10 seconds. Moreover, the figure demonstrates very good agreement between the standard deviation and the theoretical prediction based on [8]. It is worth recalling that all these signals contain the same “amount of information”, i.e., they are based on the same number of histories, detections, etc.

Figure 4. Y comparison between direct method and analog method (log-log scale)

4.5. $Y(\tau)$ and $\dot{Y}(\tau)$ variance comparison

Currently, an exact analytical expression for the variance of $\dot{Y}(\tau)$ has not been established. Consequently, its estimation relies on multiple sets of simulated histories. Fig. 5 presents the variance as a function of the set size, expressed as the proportion of histories used to compute Y in the previous analyses. The time-gate width is fixed at 1 s, and each variance value is obtained from 50 independent sets of histories. The blue line represents a fitted curve showing that the variance decrease inversely with the number of simulated histories. This is in contrast with the *analog method* whose variance decreases inversely with the the number of time gates. The figure also includes, as a red dashed line, the uncertainty of $Y(\tau = 1s)$ derived from Fig. 4a, corresponding to the nominal source intensities and using all available histories. Considering that the variance of $Y(\tau = 1s)$ for the SCRAaP experiment is approximately 0.8, this figure shows that the *direct method* achieves a comparable variance to the *analog method* while using only about 0.1% of the total simulated histories. It should be noted that this gain depends on many parameters, which are not discussed here due to the absence of a theoretical expression for the variance of the *direct method*. Nevertheless, it is obvious that this gain increases with the intensity of the signal since the fission chains tend to overlap more and more.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Traditionally, zero-power neutron noise quantities are evaluated using similar data-processing tools to analyze signals (i.e., detection events) obtained either from experimental measurements or from simulations. However, in the case of simulations, this approach is often highly CPU-intensive. The *direct method* leverages additional information available from simulations to significantly reduce statistical uncertainties—and consequently, the required computation time.

Nevertheless, the method still presents certain limitations. For instance, the treatment of detector dead time has not yet been derived, and further developments are required to extend the approach to higher-order counting statistics (e.g., triple coincidences and beyond).

Figure 5. Variance of $\hat{Y}(\tau = 1s)$ as a function of the proportion of histories used. The horizontal dashed line is the variance of the analog method.

REFERENCES

- [1] D G Langner et al. *Application Guide to Neutron Multiplicity Counting*. Tech. rep. Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM, Oct. 1998. DOI: 10.2172/1679. URL: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1679>.
- [2] A.A. Robba, E.J. Dowdy, and H.F. Atwater. “Neutron multiplication measurements using moments of the neutron counting distribution”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research* 215.3 (1983), pp. 473–479. ISSN: 0167-5087. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-5087\(83\)90481-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-5087(83)90481-7). URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0167508783904817>.
- [3] N Pacilio. *REACTOR-NOISE ANALYSIS IN THE TIME DOMAIN*. AEC Critical Review Series. Tech. rep. Argonne National Lab., Ill. Comitato Nazionale per l’Energia Nucleare, Rome (Italy), Dec. 1968. DOI: 10.2172/4786612. URL: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/4786612>.
- [4] S. Croft et al. “Feynman variance-to-mean in the context of passive neutron coincidence counting”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 686 (2012), pp. 136–144. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2012.05.042>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900212005426>.
- [5] R.P. Feynman, F. De Hoffmann, and R. Serber. “Dispersion of the neutron emission in U-235 fission”. In: *Journal of Nuclear Energy* (1954) 3.1 (1956), 64–IN10. ISSN: 0891-3919. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0891-3919\(56\)90042-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0891-3919(56)90042-0). URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0891391956900420>.
- [6] Hutchinson. *Subcritical Copper-Reflected a-phase Plutonium (SCRaP) measurements and simulations*. Korean Nuclear Society - KNS, 2024.
- [7] W. Monange and A. Bardelay. *New capabilities of the MORET 6 Monte Carlo neutron transport code*. ANS - American Nuclear Society, 2022, p. 1606–1616.
- [8] Mark A. Smith-Nelson et al. *Uncertainties of the Y_n Parameters of the Hage-Cifarelli Formalism*. Tech. rep. Los Alamos National Lab. (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States), Aug. 2015. DOI: 10.2172/1170708. URL: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1170708>.